

LETTER TO THE EDITOR

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14598695>**Protective Effect of Cyanidin-3-Glucoside on Myocardial Ischaemia-Reperfusion Injury via Ferroptosis**

Siyanidin-3-Glukozitin Ferroptoz Yoluyla Miyokardiyal İskemi-Reperfüzyon Hasarı Üzerindeki Koruyucu Etkisi

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Dear Editor,

Myocardial ischaemia-reperfusion injury (MIRI) is a complex phenomenon that occurs when blood flow to the heart is temporarily interrupted and then restored, leading to tissue damage and cell death. Ferroptosis is a newly discovered form of cell death characterised by the accumulation of lipid peroxides and iron-dependent reactive oxygen species (ROS). Cyanidin-3-glucoside (C3G) is a natural flavonoid shown to have potential protective effects against MIRI. In this article, we would like to emphasise the importance of the role of C3G in preventing MIRI through ferroptosis and call for research in a global perspective.

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